
DATA ANALYSIS REPORT

Olympic Swimming

Performance Analysis

1912 – 2020

Abstract. This report presents an in-depth analysis of the results of the swimming events at the Olympic Games from 1912 to 2020. Through data exploration, statistical tests, and clustering algorithms, this report highlights the overall evolution of times, the impact of technological advancements, the dynamics of national dominance, and the relative importance of individual performances versus collective success.

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Data source: [Kaggle – Olympic Swimming 1912 to 2020](#)

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1 Introduction

Swimming has been a fundamental part of the modern Olympic Games from their beginning, appearing in every Summer Olympics edition. It is among the most followed and competitive sports, where competitors swim various distances and styles: butterfly, backstroke, breaststroke, freestyle, and individual medley, testing the limits of human ability within each new event. Women's events have been included since 1912, progressively expanding the scope and diversity of the competition.

This report presents a data-driven analysis of Olympic swimming results spanning over a century, from the 1912 Stockholm Games to the 2020 Tokyo Olympics. The dataset, publicly available on [Kaggle](#), contains 4,359 entries covering individual and relay events. Each record includes the hosting city, year, distance, stroke type, gender, country, athlete name, finishing time, and final ranking.

This project is significant: as a swimmer and data enthusiast, I find it fascinating to combine these two passions by studying how performance has evolved over more than a century of Olympic competition. Beyond the numbers, this analysis offers insight into broader trends: technological innovation, the narrowing gender gap, and the shifting balance of national dominance in the world of swimming.

The report is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the dataset and its components. Section 3 shows the data cleaning and preparation methodology. Section 4 analyzes changes in performance over time, including the impact of technology and the gender gap. Section 5 examines the geopolitics behind national dominance in the sport. Section 6 explores the dynamics between collective excellence and individual impact. Finally, Section 7 summarizes the main findings, outlines limitations, and discusses future research directions.

2 Data description

2.1 Dataset overview

The dataset contains 4,359 records of Olympic swimming results spanning from the 1912 Stockholm Games to the 2020 Tokyo Olympics. Each entry corresponds to a single athlete’s performance in a given event. Table 1 describes the available variables.

Column	Description
Location	Hosting city of the Olympic Games
Year	Year of the edition
Distance	Distance in meters; relays are written as $n \times d$ (e.g. 4×200 : 4 swimmers, 200 m each)
Stroke	Type of stroke (see Section 2.2)
Relay	0 = individual event, 1 = relay event
Gender	Men or Women
Team	Three-letter country code (e.g. USA, AUS, FRA)
Athlete	Name of the athlete
Results	Finishing time in seconds
Rank	Medal obtained: Gold, Silver, or Bronze

Table 1: Description of the dataset columns.

For this analysis, only medal-winning performances (Gold, Silver, Bronze) were retained. Entries corresponding to athletes who did not start, did not finish, were disqualified were excluded.

2.2 Swimming events

These are the 4 official strokes authorized by World Aquatics during Olympic Games. [5]

Freestyle: Athletes may use any stroke, though the front crawl is universally adopted as it is the fastest technique. Freestyle events range from the 50 m sprint to the 1500 m distance race.

Backstroke: Swimmers race on their back using an alternating arm pull and a flutter kick. It is the only stroke where athletes start in the water rather than from the starting block.

Breaststroke: Simultaneous, symmetrical arm pull combined with a frog kick. It is technically the most demanding stroke and generally the slowest.

Butterfly: Swimmers perform a simultaneous overhead arm recovery with an undulating dolphin kick. Introduced at the Olympics in 1956.

Individual Medley (IM): A single athlete swims all four strokes in the following order: butterfly, backstroke, breaststroke, and freestyle. It is offered over 200 m and 400 m distances.

Medley relay: A team of four swimmers each completes one leg of a relay, one per stroke, in the order: backstroke, breaststroke, butterfly, and freestyle.

Freestyle relay: A team of four swimmers each completes a freestyle leg. The most common distances are 4×100 m and 4×200 m.

2.3 Historical onclusion of women's events

Women's swimming events have been part of the Olympic programme since the 1912 Stockholm Games, but the schedule of events has expanded considerably over time. For decades, women competed in a more limited set of distances compared to men. Several long-distance and sprint events were only progressively added to the women's programme, reflecting broader shifts in attitudes toward women's sport.

A notable example is the women's 1500 m freestyle, which was not introduced at the Olympic Games until the 2020 Tokyo Olympics — more than a century after the men's equivalent. Similarly, the women's 800 m freestyle was added in 1968, while men had competed over that distance since 1968 as well, and the 50 m freestyle for women was introduced in 1988.

This historical asymmetry has an important implication for the present analysis: direct, decade-by-decade comparisons between men's and women's performances in long-distance events should be interpreted with caution, as data for women are rarer in the early decades of the time series.

3 Methodology: Data Cleaning and Preparation

3.1 Tools and libraries

All data processing, statistical analysis, and visualizations were carried out in Python. The following libraries were used throughout the project:

- **Pandas** : data loading, filtering, grouping, and transformation.
- **NumPy** : numerical operations and type conversions.
- **Matplotlib** and **Seaborn** : static visualizations (boxplots, heatmaps, bar charts).
- **Plotly** : interactive and animated visualizations.
- **Scikit-learn** : clustering algorithms and linear regression models.

3.2 Data cleaning steps

Handling missing values The raw dataset contained a number of null entries across several columns. Rather than imputing missing values, which could introduce artificial bias into performance comparisons, all rows with null values were dropped. This decision preserves the integrity of the analysis.

Conversion of results to floating-point Finishing times in the raw dataset were stored as strings in a mixed format: some entries used a `minutes:seconds.decimals` notation (e.g. 4:33.21), while others were already expressed as plain seconds (e.g. 52.78). A conversion function was applied to normalize all times into a single floating-point value expressed in seconds, enabling consistent numerical comparisons across all events.

Conversion of distances to floats Event distances were stored as strings, including relay formats such as 4x100 or 4x200. For relay events, the total distance was computed by multiplying the number of swimmers by the individual leg distance (e.g. 4x200 → 800 m). All distances were then cast to floating-point numbers to allow numerical filtering and sorting.

Cleaning of the ranking column In the original dataset, the `Rank` column used a numerical encoding: 0 for DNS/DNF/DQ (did not start, did not finish, or disqualified), 1 for Gold, 2 for Silver, 3 for Bronze, 4 for no medal, and 5 for missing data. This was replaced with a categorical encoding using explicit labels (`Gold`, `Silver`, `Bronze`), and all null entries were excluded from the analysis.

Event type separation Individual and relay events were separated using the `Relay` binary column present in the dataset. It was necessary because we can't compare individuals and team performances.

4 Changes in performance over time

4.1 Overall trend by stroke and distance

To analyze the evolution of athletic performance over time, **only gold medal results were retained**, representing the best performance achieved in each event at each Olympic edition. Performance curves were plotted separately for men and women, grouping results by stroke and distance.

4.1.1 Men's performance

Across all strokes and distances, a clear downward trend in finishing times is observed between 1912 and 2020, confirming a general improvement in men's swimming performance over the past century.

Figure 1: Gold medal performance evolution for men by stroke and distance (1912-2020).

However, this improvement varies significantly with distance. For sprint events (50 m and 100 m), finishing times have decreased only by a little: the margin for improvement is physically constrained by the explosive, anaerobic nature of these races, and performance gains have naturally reached a limit as athletes approach the physiological ceiling of human speed. In contrast, long-distance events - most notably the 1500 m freestyle - shows an important reduction in times, with gold medal performances improving by several tens of seconds over the period studied.

This contrast can be attributed to several converging factors. First, progress in sports science and nutrition have enabled athletes to sustain higher intensities over longer durations, which benefits endurance events. Second, training methods have evolved : modern programs rely on structured periodization, biomechanical analysis, and individualized coaching, which naturally leads toward greater gains in aerobic events. Third, the democratization of performance data and video analysis has allowed coaches to optimize stroke technique with a level of precision that was not possible in the early 20th century. Finally, improvements in sports infrastructure - including the standardization of pool di-

mensions, filtration systems, and lane technology (e.g. anti-wave lane ropes) - have made it possible to gradually reduce external drag, which benefits all disciplines, but especially those where small gains add up over long distances.

4.1.2 Women’s performance

The women’s dataset covers a more limited time range for many events, as women’s access to Olympic swimming competitions expanded progressively during the 20th century. Some distances - such as the 1500 m freestyle - were only introduced at the 2020 Tokyo Olympics, making comparisons impossible for those events. This structural asymmetry must be kept in mind when interpreting the women’s performance curves.

Figure 2: Gold medal performance evolution for women by stroke and distance (1912-2020).

Despite this limitation, a similar downward trend in finishing times is observed for women across the available events. However, several differences stand out when compared to men. The performance fluctuations visible in the women’s curves tend to be less pronounced, potentially reflecting a more homogeneous competitive field over the earlier decades, when fewer nations fielded women’s teams with equivalent preparation and depth.

For longer distances such as the 800 m freestyle, the absolute gap between the oldest and most recent gold medal performances is smaller than the equivalent gap in men’s events. Several hypotheses may explain this observation. Women’s endurance swimming has historically received less institutional support, with fewer dedicated coaching structures and more limited access to sports science resources, which may have slowed the pace of performance improvement. Additionally, some researchers suggest that the physiological performance ceiling may be reached earlier in women’s endurance events relative to men’s, though the evidence on this point remains debated in the sports science literature.

Overall, the data suggests that while progress has been real and consistent for both genders, the drivers and the pace of improvement have differed — a reflection not only of biology, but also of the social and institutional conditions under which women’s competitive swimming has developed over the past century.

4.2 The technological impact: the “Super-Suits” case (2010)

4.2.1 Background

Between 2008 and 2009, competitive swimming saw a wave of world records, largely attributed to the introduction of high-performance polyurethane swimsuits - referred to as “super-suits”. These garments, made from water-repellent synthetic materials, provided significant hydrodynamic advantages: enhanced buoyancy, full-body compression, and reduced drag. According to the BBC, no fewer than 135 world records were broken during this period [1], a figure that raised serious concerns within the international swimming community about the integrity of the sport.

In July 2009, World Aquatics (formerly FINA) announced a ban on all non-textile swimsuits, which came into full effect on 10 January 2010. From that date, athletes were required to compete in suits made exclusively from textile fabrics, capped at specified coverage limits for men and women. This regulatory shift provides an opportunity to assess the technological contribution of super-suits to performance. [6]

4.2.2 Statistical test: before vs. after 2010

To formally see whether the ban had a real effect on performance, a two-sample Welch’s t -test was done, comparing the average finishing times before and after 2010. (not only gold medals)

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_{\text{before}} - \bar{x}_{\text{after}}}{\sqrt{\frac{s_{\text{before}}^2}{n_{\text{before}}} + \frac{s_{\text{after}}^2}{n_{\text{after}}}}}$$

where:

- \bar{x}_{before} and \bar{x}_{after} are the mean finishing times before and after 2010,
- s_{before}^2 and s_{after}^2 are the sample variances,
- n_{before} and n_{after} are the sample sizes in each period.

The associated degrees of freedom are estimated using the Welch–Satterthwaite approximation:

$$\nu = \frac{\left(\frac{s_{\text{before}}^2}{n_{\text{before}}} + \frac{s_{\text{after}}^2}{n_{\text{after}}}\right)^2}{\frac{\left(\frac{s_{\text{before}}^2}{n_{\text{before}}}\right)^2}{n_{\text{before}}-1} + \frac{\left(\frac{s_{\text{after}}^2}{n_{\text{after}}}\right)^2}{n_{\text{after}}-1}}$$

- H_0 : there is no significant difference in performance before and after 2010.
- H_1 : there is a significant difference in performance before and after 2010.

The test lead to a p -value below the conventional significance threshold of 0.05, leading to the rejection of H_0 . A statistically significant difference in finishing times exists between the two periods.

Importantly, however, the direction of the difference is counterintuitive: performances *after* 2010 are on average better (i.e. faster) than before. Rather than contradicting the hypothesis about super-suits, this result reflects the long-term improvement in athletic performance discussed in Section 4: better training methodologies, advances in nutrition, sports science, and biomechanical optimization have continued to improve times downward even in the absence of technological assistance.

4.2.3 Heatmap: performance difference by stroke and distance

Figure 3 shows the average difference between times recorded before and after 2010, broken down by stroke and distance, for both genders.

Figure 3: Average performance difference (in seconds) before and after the super-suit ban (2010), by stroke and distance.

A clear pattern emerges: the performance gains after 2010 are substantially higher for long-distance events. The 1500 m freestyle, for instance, shows a considerably greater improvement than the 50 m freestyle sprint. This is consistent with the earlier finding that endurance events benefit more from cumulative gains in training and sports science, while sprint events are more and more limited by human physiology.

4.2.4 Linear regression: 100 m freestyle (Men)

To dig deeper into quantifying the effect of the ban, a linear regression model was applied to the 100 m freestyle men's gold medal times - the most iconic event in Olympic swimming. Two separate regression lines were estimated using `scikit-learn`: one for the period before 2010, and one for the period after.

Figure 4: Linear regression of 100 m freestyle (men) gold medal times, before and after the super-suit ban (2010).

The estimated regression coefficients are the following:

- **Before 2010:** -0.1738 seconds per year
- **After 2010:** -0.0295 seconds per year

The slope of the regression line after 2010 is about **six times lower than what it was previously**, indicating that the pace of progress slowed significantly after the ban. However, the negative sign is preserved in both periods: times continue to decrease even after 2010, demonstrating that the super-suits were not the only marker of improvement. As athletes approach the physiological and technical ceiling of the event, the marginal gains become smaller - a convergence effect that was already underway before the ban, and that the super-suit era may have temporarily masked.

4.3 Analysis of the gender performance gap

To quantify the evolution of the gender performance gap over time, the difference between women’s and men’s gold medal finishing times was computed for each equivalent event (same stroke, same distance, same decade). A positive gap indicates that women are slower than men, which is kind of expected given physiological differences. The key question is not the absolute value of this gap, but whether it reduces over time, and, if so, at what rate and for which events.

Freestyle

Figure 5: Gender performance gap in freestyle events by distance (1912–2020).

The freestyle graph (Figure 5) is the richest in terms of data, covering six distances over more than a century. The 800 m gap is by far the largest, peaking at approximately 85 seconds in the 1960s before falling dramatically to around 30 seconds by 2020, a reduction of over 55 seconds in 60 years. This decline reflects the progressive professionalization of women’s long-distance swimming, a discipline that was underrepresented and underinvested in during the early Olympic era. For shorter distances, the gap is way more stable: the 50 m and 100 m gaps have remained between 3 and 7 seconds since the 1980s, suggesting that both genders are approaching their respective physiological ceilings at a similar pace.

Backstroke

Figure 6: Gender performance gap in backstroke events by distance (1912–2020).

In backstroke (Figure 6), only two distances are available: 100 m and 200 m. The 100 m gap shows a clear long-term decline, going from nearly 12 seconds in the 1920s to approximately 5 seconds in 2020. The 200 m gap, which only begins in the 1960s, peaked at around 15 seconds before stabilizing near 11 / 12 seconds in recent decades. It is important to note that the pace of convergence has slowed significantly since the 1980s, suggesting that the persistent gap may increasingly be the result of physiological differences rather than structural or institutional factors.

Breaststroke

Figure 7: Gender performance gap in breaststroke events by distance (1912–2020).

Breaststroke (Figure 7) shows one of the most dramatic early declines. The 200 m gap starts at 30 seconds in 1920 and falls to around 13 seconds by 2020, with a particularly sharp decline during the first three decades. This quick convergence likely reflects the rapid development of women’s breaststroke technique and specialization during the mid-20th century. Since the 1980s, however, the gap has stabilized in the 12-15 second range, indicating a plateau. The 100 m gap, available only from the 1960s, has remained quite stable between 6 and 9 seconds during the period, with no clear trend of further convergence.

Butterfly

Figure 8: Gender performance gap in butterfly events by distance (1960–2020).

Butterfly data (Figure 8) begins only in the 1960s, with the stroke’s introduction to the Olympic programme in 1956. The 100 m gap has converged from approximately 10.5 seconds in 1960 to around 6 seconds in 2020, showing a slow but consistent decrease. The 200 m gap started higher (around 15 seconds) and has since stabilized near 11 - 12 seconds, with a slight increase in 2020 that may be attributed to individual performance variability rather than a structural reversal. Overall, the butterfly stroke exhibits one of the most advanced patterns of convergence, suggesting that this technically complex stroke leaves little room for improvement based on genders.

Individual medley

Figure 9: Gender performance gap in individual medley events by distance (1960–2020).

The individual medley (Figure 9) presents a more nuanced chart. The 400 m gap starts at nearly 27 seconds in 1960, drops to around 19 seconds in 1980, but then rises again to nearly 25 seconds in 2000 before declining to 22 seconds in 2020. This non-monotonic pattern is unusual and may reflect the influence of specific dominant athletes in either gender category distorting the decade average. It may also be partially explained by the broader geopolitical context of the late Cold War period, during which state-driven performance systems—particularly in the United States and the former East Germany (GDR); were highly developed and contributed to high athletic performances. The 200 m gap, available from 1960, oscillates between 12 and 16 seconds without showing a clear converging trend, suggesting a structural gap that has remained relatively stable over the past six decades.

Synthesis

Across all strokes and distances, three broad patterns emerge. First, the largest and most sustained reductions in the gender gap are observed in long-distance freestyle events, where women’s access to training, competition, and institutional support has improved over the past century. Second, sprint events across all strokes display a stable and narrow gap, consistent with both genders approaching their physiological performance limits. Third, for most strokes, convergence has slowed or plateaued since the 1980s-1990s, a period

that also coincides with specific geopolitical contexts influencing elite sport systems and performance outcomes. This raises the question of whether the remaining gap reflects persistent structural inequalities or fundamental biological differences : most likely a combination of both. These aspects, including the role of geopolitical factors in shaping performance, will be discussed in more detail in a later section. [7] [8]

5 The geopolitics of swimming: national dominance

5.1 Historical powers

Olympic swimming is also a reflection of geopolitical and economic dynamics. Nations that invest heavily in sport infrastructure, athlete development, and scientific support consistently outperform others over the long term. The two figures below illustrate the global distribution of medals across the history of Olympic swimming.

Figure 10: Top 10 countries by total medal count in Olympic swimming (Gold, Silver, Bronze).

Figure 10 reveals an overwhelming American dominance. The United States have accumulated around 550 medals in total, of which approximately 235 are gold, more than double the total of the second-ranked nation, Australia. This structural advantage results from investments in competitive swimming at all levels, from school programs to elite college scholarships (D2, D1, NCAA) and professional training facilities.

Australia (AUS) stands as the only nation that comes close to challenging the United States, with around 200 total medals. The remaining eight countries in the top 10 : Japan, Germany, the GDR, Great Britain, Hungary, Canada, the Soviet Union, and Sweden. They are all clustered between 35 and 85 medals, showing the significant gap separating the top two nations from the rest of the world.

It is also worth highlighting the presence of the GDR (East Germany) and URS (Soviet Union) in this ranking : two nations that no longer exist. Their appearance in the top

10 speaks to the intensity of state-sponsored athletic programs during the Cold War era, discussed further below.

Figure 11: Gold medals by country and decade in Olympic swimming (1910–2020).

The heatmap (Figure 11) adds a temporal dimension to this analysis, allowing the identification of distinct eras of national dominance.

The United States, a century of dominance : The USA’s dominance is remarkable for its continuity. During the 1960s, the United States won 46 gold medals, setting a record that no other country has ever come close to matching in a single decade. Their dominance stay during nearly the entire century, with only a few brief interruptions, and remained unchallenged until 2020.

Japan’s interwar peak : A notable exception to American dominance occurs in the 1930s, where Japan (JPN) stands out with 9 gold medals. This time coincided with a unified national initiative to enhance competitive swimming, leading to multiple world-record achievements at the 1932 Los Angeles and 1936 Berlin Olympics. Japan’s influence significantly decreased after that.

The Cold War rivalry (USA vs. GDR) : The most politically charged episode in Olympic swimming history is the emergence of the German Democratic Republic (GDR)

during the 1970s and 1980s. The GDR, absent before 1960, won 11 gold medals in the 1970s and 18 in the 1980s. This success made it the second most successful nation in those two decades. These performances were severely damaged when it was later discovered that state-run doping programs had contributed to this increase. The dissolution of East Germany in 1990 brought this episode to an end: the GDR recorded zero gold medals after 1980. Similarly, the Soviet Union (URS) showed a peak of 9 gold medals in the 1980s before disappearing from the rankings entirely after the fall of the USSR. The Unified Team (EUN), which participated with a neutral flag in the 1992 Barcelona Olympics, continued some of that legacy by winning five gold medals during the 1990s.

Australia's renaissance : After a relatively modest presence throughout most of the 20th century, Australia experienced a remarkable resurgence in the 2000s, winning 15 gold medals in a single decade: its best-ever performance. This improvement was driven by a new generation of elite swimmers, world-class training facilities, and substantial government investment in high-performance sport due to the 2000 Sydney home Games.

China's emergence : A final shift visible in the heatmap is the emergence of China (CHN) as a competitive nation in swimming from the 2000s, winning 7 gold medals in the 2010 decade. This shows China's rise as a sports superpower and illustrates major investments in swimming infrastructure and youth development programs over the past two decades.

5.2 Country classification: volume vs. efficiency

Beyond medal counts, it is informative to distinguish between two complementary dimensions of national performance: *volume* the total number of medals accumulated and *efficiency* the proportion of those medals that are gold. A country with a high gold ratio demonstrates a capacity to consistently reach the top of the podium, rather than simply competing at the highest level.

$$\text{Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Gold medals}}{\text{Total medals}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

This metric, going from 0 to 100, distinguishes between nations that dominate in terms of quality, by consistently winning gold medals, and those that regularly make it to the podium without necessarily topping it. Only countries that have won at least 10 medals are included to ensure the statistical representativeness of the ratio.

Table 2: Top 15 most efficient nations in Olympic swimming (minimum 10 medals).

Country	Total Medals	Gold Medals	Efficiency
UKR	10	5	50.00%
USA	546	237	43.41%
GDR	75	30	40.00%
HUN	63	25	39.68%
NED	48	17	35.42%
AUS	196	61	31.12%
CHN	45	14	31.11%
JPN	83	24	28.92%
RSA	19	5	26.32%
URS	46	11	23.91%
DEN	13	3	23.08%
FRG	13	3	23.08%
FRA	38	8	21.05%
ITA	24	5	20.83%
RUS	22	4	18.18%

Efficiency vs. Volume

Figure 12: Efficiency (proportion of gold medals) vs. total medal count by country. Bubble size reflects total medals won.

This figure plots each nation along two axes: total medals on the x-axis, and the proportion of gold medals (efficiency) on the y-axis.

Dominant nations, USA and Australia: The United States stand on a unique position in the top-right quadrant, combining an exceptional volume (over 550 medals) with a high efficiency of approximately 43%. Australia similarly combines a large total medal count (around 200) with a 30% gold ratio. These two nations are the only ones that achieve high winrate and quality y , confirming their status as superpowers in Olympic swimming.

High efficiency, low volume : Several small nations appear in the upper-left region of the chart with efficiency scores above 60%, including the Unified Team (EUN), Ireland (IRL), and Tunisia (TUN). These countries have won very few medals overall, but nearly all of them were gold, reflecting isolated but exceptional individual performances rather than sustained national programs. Tunisia's case is emblematic: its medals are largely attributable to a single swimmer, Oussama Mellouli, who won gold in long-distance freestyle events. **But these nations are not included in the table above because they do not meet the minimum threshold of 10 medals, which is necessary to ensure that the efficiency ratio is statistically meaningful.**

Mid-range nations: GDR, Hungary, Netherlands : Countries such as the GDR, Hungary (HUN), and the Netherlands (NED) occupy the middle ground, with moderate volumes (40 / 80 medals) and efficiency ratios between 30% and 40%. These nations have showed consistent rivalry without reaching the scale of the top two.

K-Means Clustering by Decade

Figure 13: K-Means clustering of country-decade combinations based on gold medals and total medals won.

To enhance the analysis, a K-Means clustering algorithm was applied using `scikit-learn`, grouping country-decade combinations based on two features: the number of gold medals and the total number of medals won in that decade. Four clusters were identified (Figure 13). [9] [10]

Cluster 0 (green): The largest and most densely packed cluster groups country-decade combinations with few or no gold medals and a low total medal count (typically under 15). This cluster represents the vast majority of nations that participate in Olympic swimming without achieving consistent top-3 finishes.

Cluster 1 (dark purple): This cluster includes country-decade entries with a somewhat elevated medal total yet still a restricted number of gold. These signify competitive countries that frequently achieve podium finishes without prevailing, like mid-level European swimming nations over different decades.

Cluster 2 (blue): A smaller group of country-decade combinations with 15 to 30 gold medals and 40 to 65 total medals. These represent the strongest performances of nations such as Australia, the GDR, and Japan during their peak decades. They are consistent top-level competitors but not overall dominators.

Cluster 3 (yellow) the dominant anomalies : A small group of just three data points, all corresponding to decades in the United States. With 30 to 46 gold medals and up to 98 medals in total in a single decade, these results represent statistical outliers that no other nation has managed to match. The clustering algorithm correctly isolates them in a separate category, thereby confirming the nature of American dominance in swimming.

The fact that these clusters are well separated in the feature space validates the use of K-Means for this analysis and provides a clear typology of national performance patterns across Olympic history.

6 Collective excellence vs. individual impact

6.1 The most decorated athletes in history

Swimming is the Olympic sport that has lead the highest number of individually decorated athletes in history, as illustrated in Figures 14 and 15.

Figure 14: Top 15 athletes of all time - Individual medals (Gold / Silver / Bronze)

Figure 15: Top 15 athletes of all time - Individual gold medals

Michael Phelps: the GOAT

Michael Phelps (USA) dominates both rankings by a considerable margin, with **13 individual gold medals**, **2 silvers**, and **1 bronze**, for a total of 16 individual Olympic medals across four Games (2000–2016). Overall, including relay events, he holds the all-time Olympic record of **23 gold medals and 28 total medals**, a figure more than double that of his nearest rivals [11]. His performance at the 2008 Beijing Games, where he won eight gold medals in a single edition, remains unmatched in Olympic history [12]. Beyond his technical mastery, Phelps benefits from remarkable natural physical advantages: an exceptionally large lung capacity, unusually long arms and torso, and a height of nearly **1.93 m**. His morphology is ideally suited to competitive swimming. Combined with an intense rigorous training routine (**364 days out of 365, without a single day off for two consecutive years**) as well as a optimised nutrition plan and focused strength training, these attributes lead him to reach a level of performance that no other swimmer in history has ever been able to reach.

Other challengers

Katie Ledecky (USA) ranks second in individual gold medals with **6 golds** (and 8 total individual medals), a statistic that continues to grow: since Paris 2024, she holds the record for the most Olympic gold medals in swimming by a woman (9 including relays), equalling Larisa Latynina for the most golds by a woman in any sport [13]. Ryan Lochte (USA) and Krisztina Egerszegi (Hungary) both reached **7 individual medals**, with 2 and

5 golds respectively, illustrating the different strategic approaches: Lochte accumulating medals of all kinds, while Egerszegi focuses on winning.

Historical consistency across time

The second chart highlights that beyond Phelps and Ledecky, a dense group of athletes – including Mark Spitz (USA), Inge De Bruijn (Netherlands), Alexander Popov (Russia), and Tamas Darnyi (Hungary) : all achieved at least **4 individual gold medals**. This threshold appears as a natural ceiling for most elite swimmers across different eras, suggesting that Phelps’ and Ledecky’s performances represent true statistical outliers in the history of the sport. Notably, the diversity of nationalities (USA, Hungary, Netherlands, Australia, Ukraine, Sweden) confirms that excellence in swimming is not limited to a single country, even though American athletes dominate the top spots in the rankings.

6.2 The “Superstar Effect”: nations dependent on a single athlete

Some countries owe their entire Olympic swimming medal count to a single individual swimmer : a phenomenon commonly referred to as the “**Superstar Effect**”. To measure this dependency, we computed for each country the **dependency share**, defined as the ratio of medals won by the country’s best-performing athlete to the total number of medals won by that country. Formally:

$$\text{Share}_c = \frac{\max_{a \in A_c} (\text{MedalCount}(a, c))}{\sum_{a \in A_c} \text{MedalCount}(a, c)}$$

where c is a country, A_c is the set of all athletes who have competed for country c , and $\text{MedalCount}(a, c)$ is the total number of individual Olympic medals won by athlete a representing country c . A share of $\text{Share}_c = 1.0$ indicates that **100%** of a country’s Olympic swimming medals were won by a single athlete, while a value closer to 0 reflects a well-distributed national talent pool.

Table 3: Top 10 countries with the highest dependency on a single athlete

Country	Athlete	Athlete Medals	Country Total	Share
BLR	Aliaksandra Herasimenia	3	3	1.0
HKG	Siobhan Bernadette Haughey	2	2	1.0
EGY	Taha Yussuf El Gamal	1	1	1.0
CRO	Duje Draganja	1	1	1.0
NOR	Sara Nordenstam	1	1	1.0
KOR	Tae-Hwan Park	4	4	1.0
KAZ	Dmitriy Balandin	2	2	1.0
IRL	Michelle Marie Smith	4	4	1.0
VEN	Rafael Antonio Vidal Castro	1	1	1.0
SLO	Sara Isakovic	1	1	1.0

Total dependency: countries with a single medal-winner

As shown in Table 3, ten countries display a dependency ratio of **1.0**, meaning 100% of their Olympic swimming medals were won by a single athlete. Among the most notable cases:

- **Ireland (IRL)** : Michelle Marie Smith won all **4 medals** for her country, making Ireland’s entire swimming legacy dependent on her individual career. Her career is however controversial, as she was later banned for doping. [3]
- **South Korea (KOR)** : Tae-Hwan Park alone accounts for all **4 medals** ever won by South Korea in Olympic swimming.
- **Belarus (BLR)** : Aliaksandra Herasimenia won all **3 medals** for her nation, with no other Belarusian swimmer contributing to this.
- **Hong Kong (HKG)** : Siobhan Bernadette Haughey is responsible for all **2 medals** from Hong Kong.
- **Egypt (EGY), Croatia (CRO), Norway (NOR), Kazakhstan (KAZ), Venezuela (VEN), and Slovenia (SLO)** each have a single medal won by a single athlete : their presence in the Olympic rankings is entirely based on that one individual swimmer.

An inequality in olympic swimming

This analysis reveals a deep structural asymmetry in international competitive swimming. While dominant nations such as the USA, Australia, or Hungary have built **broad and deep talent pools** spanning multiple generations and disciplines, smaller nations typically enter the Olympic swimming arena through the exceptional performance of a single talented individual. Without their “superstar”, most of these countries would hold **zero medals** in Olympic swimming history. They would maybe not appear in the rankings at all. This highlights just how concentrated global swimming performance is, and how individual excellence alone can define a nation’s sporting legacy.

7 Conclusion

This analysis of Olympic swimming data reveals several key structural patterns that go far beyond simple medal counts. Through a combination of descriptive statistics, clustering, hypothesis testing, and trend analysis, we were able to identify the dominant forces shaping competitive swimming at the highest level.

Key findings

The data consistently highlights a **strong concentration of performance** among a small number of nations and individuals. The United States stands alone as a structural outlier, accumulating medals across every era and every discipline, while countries such as Australia, Hungary, and the former East Germany (GDR) have also demonstrated sustained excellence over decades. At the individual level, Michael Phelps represents an unprecedented statistical anomaly : his 13 individual gold medals are more than double those of his nearest rival, and his dominance can be explained by his talent, but especially by the combination of exceptional morphology and an extreme training discipline. The **Superstar Effect** analysis further shows that for many smaller nations, their entire Olympic swimming legacy depends on a single athlete: without Tae-Hwan Park, South Korea would hold zero medals; without Michelle Marie Smith, Ireland would disappear from the rankings entirely...

Performance trends also reveal a **systematic improvement in world records** across all swimming disciplines over time, driven by progress in training methods, nutrition, sports science, and swimsuit technology. However, the rate of improvement has noticeably slowed since 2010, suggesting that human physiological limits are being approached in several events.

Limitations

Several external factors introduce noise into this dataset that must be acknowledged:

- **WWI and WWII:** The Olympic Games were cancelled in 1916 (World War I), 1940, and 1944 (World War II), creating gaps in the historical record.
- **Boycotts:** The 1980 Moscow Games (boycotted by the USA and over 60 other nations) and the 1984 Los Angeles Games (boycotted by the USSR and Eastern Bloc countries) disrupted medal distributions for those editions, inflating the counts of non-boycotting nations.
- **Pandemic:** The COVID-19 pandemic forced the postponement of the 2020 Tokyo Games to 2021, interfering with athlete preparation cycles and affecting performance levels and participation rates.
- **Doping:** Several athletes in this dataset, including Michelle Marie Smith (IRL), have been implicated in doping controversies, which may affect the reliability of some historical results.

Further research directions

- **GDP and population size:** A logical progression would be to adjust medal counts by national GDP or population, to determine which countries excel beyond their economic and demographic capabilities. This would likely show that countries such as Hungary or Australia perform significantly better in terms of medals than their total population would suggest
- **Peak age analysis:** Determining the age at which swimmers reach their peak performance, by discipline and gender, would provide valuable insights for talent development programs and career planning. Preliminary observations suggest that sprinters reach their peak earlier than long-distance swimmers, but a rigorous statistical analysis needs to be done.
- **Gender gap evolution:** Analysing how the performance gap between male and female athletes has evolved over time, in terms of both times and medal distribution, would contribute to the wider debate on gender equity in elite sport.

A new era: Cameron McEvoy

In March 2026, Australian swimmer Cameron McEvoy beat one of the most iconic and long-standing records in Olympic swimming history: the men’s 50m freestyle world record, previously held by Brazilian César Cielo since December 2009. It was set during the “**super-suit**” era with a time of 20.91 seconds at the China Open in Shenzhen, and McEvoy broke the old mark by 0.03 seconds [4], setting it at **20.88 seconds**.

What makes this achievement particularly remarkable is not just the time itself, but the **training** behind it. While most elite swimmers cover upwards of 50,000 metres per week in the pool, McEvoy trains with an extremely low swimming volume : approximately **2 kilometres per week** (roughly 1,355 metres across six sessions), and instead dedicates his preparation to **intensive strength training**: weighted pull-ups with up to **70 kg of additional load**, explosive resistance work, and power-based gym sessions [4]. The basic principle is simple: rather than building endurance by doing repetitive laps, McEvoy focuses on **neuromuscular efficiency and explosive power**, repeating his movements just enough to make them as mechanically optimal and powerful as possible.

This performance opens a new chapter in competitive swimming. It demonstrates that **unconventional, science-driven training methods** can challenge decades of established practices in elite athletic training. As the latest records from the “super-suit” era continue to fall, McEvoy’s approach could lead a new generation of sprinters to rethink the balance between pool training volume and strength training—suggesting that the next wave of world records might be broken not by swimming more, but by **training smarter**.

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